

HyDelta 3

WP2a – Standalone Hydrogen Areas in the Netherlands

D2a.3 – Electrolyzer business case in a standalone hydrogen area and the effect of adding firm/non-firm grid tariffs

Status: final

Document summary

Corresponding author

Corresponding author	Javier Fatou Gómez
Affiliation	Nederlandse Organisatie voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek (TNO)
Email address	Javier.fatougomez@tno.nl

Document history

Version	Date	Author	Affiliation	Summary of main changes
1	3-Oct-2024	Javier Fatou Gómez, Aitazaz Raja	TNO	Draft version.
2	16-Oct-2024	Javier Fatou Gómez, Aitazaz Raja, Femke Janssen	TNO	Draft version after feedback, added Samenvatting.
3	10-Dec-2024	Javier Fatou Gómez, Aitazaz Raja, Femke Janssen	TNO	Final version after feedback.

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
-----------	--------	---

Document review

Partner	Name
NEC	Rob van Zoelen
Stedin	Tjebbe Vroon, Frank van Alphen
Enexis	Chantal Spierings
NBNL	HyDelta Supervisory Group (Tom Eijsackers)

Tag (Choose only ONE):

Technology and Safety

- Activities (e.g. maintenance, purging etc.)
- Assets
- Digitalisation
- End use
- Gas network
- QRA

Social aspects

- Conversion (of the distribution network)
- Education

Social

System and Economy

- Business Development
- Production and supply
- Value chains

Gas Quality

- Admixing
- Gas Quality
- Odourisation

Executive summary

With increasingly higher amounts of renewable, fluctuating power expected by 2040 and 2050, electricity grid congestion is a difficult challenge to be faced by the grid operators in The Netherlands, both at transmission and distribution levels. Current mechanisms to mitigate grid congestion, such as long-term grid reinforcement, can be very costly and/or unfeasible to match these targets, due to reasons such as land availability, specialized labour or raw material scarcity. Bilateral agreements for re-dispatching can also be expensive, and it may affect several parties within the value chain. The limitations in power availability due to current and future grid congestion are relevant when considering the business case of new assets that consume power, such as electrolyzers.

This study analyses the effect in the business case of an electrolyzer of contract-based strategies at the Distribution System Operator (DSO) level, when combining a multi-energy asset of power generation (solar) and consumption (electrolyzer) within the same asset owner. The case study chosen is inspired by the H2 Hollandia pilot in Drenthe, with 115 MW of solar power and a 5 MW electrolyzer. Following the spirit of the ATR85 proposal for transmission rights, a similar set of tariffs is set here: 15% power can be restricted at selected time slots, providing in exchange a reduction in the grid tariff (non-firm tariffs). It is investigated if this can positively affect the business case of the electrolyzer, using the Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCoH) as a metric. In addition, subcases restricting consumption *and* generation and an exploration of different relative sizes of the electrolyzer and the grid availability for a fixed solar park and firm/non-firm have been explored. These cases have been tested for two purchasing strategies of green power: purchasing from any source *only when it is fully green* (using grid price as a proxy to determine this at flexible pricing based on the market rate) or with a dedicated wind farm with a fixed Power Purchase Agreement (PPA) price. The explicit impact on the distribution grid in an area and at a particular substation has not been modelled in this study, and only qualitative insights in this aspect can be considered.

The results of the study indicate that, if the infrastructure and other conditions (e.g., off-taker agreements) are present, grid tariffs could be one of the relevant incentives (in combination with others) to bring hydrogen production to certain areas. The best result was achieved with the flexible pricing purchasing strategy, where a reduction of around 0.3 EUR/kg was achieved in the LCoH when using a non-firm grid tariff compared to a firm tariff. In this case, the grid tariff was reduced from around 150 EUR/MWh to around 70 EUR/MWh, for less than 1% of reduction of the utilization factor of the electrolyzer due to the restrictions in consumption.

However, this positive effect was not always observed. For the fixed PPA strategy, the LCoH remained approximately constant for firm and non-firm tariffs. This is due to the fact that the reduction in tariff and utilization factor of the electrolyzer had approximately the same positive and negative effects, respectively, with less OPEX but less hydrogen production. A modest decrease in the monthly LCoH profiles variability was achieved, resulting in a more stable overall LCoH along the year.

Introducing a second component of a grid tariff reduction, by reducing further the consumption tariff but restricting generation as well (suitable for assets with both generation and consumption), did not result in a positive impact in the LCoH compared to the other flexible tariffs for the conditions tested.

In a sizing optimization study of the electrolyzer capacity and the grid connection/PPA usage for a fixed solar park, flexible grid tariffs usually promoted solutions with more usage from the grid. In the case of a fixed PPA pricing scheme, a region with larger electrolyzer sizes (in the order of 20 MW, compared to the original 5 MW) were seen as the most cost-effective solutions regarding the LCoH.

This work highlights that non-firm tariffs could potentially present an opportunity to encourage the placement of electrolyzers in certain areas and/or to improve the business case of a system composed of renewable energy assets and an electrolyzer. However, their specific implementation may require significant tailoring to each asset/value chain. The willingness of flexible delivery of hydrogen from the side of the off-taker, purchasing agreement strategies, and also other elements out of scope of this study, such as energy storage solutions, are elements that may largely affect the impact of these tariffs. In addition, this study only included restrictions at random times within specific months and hours. In certain substations, patterns may be present that could allow for further benefits, synergizing the flexibility of the asset and the grid tariff contract conditions. These, and a more holistic analysis at qualitative/quantitative level of the costs associated with reducing congestion outside of the asset owner, such as at DSO and societal levels, could lead to other positive dimensions which were not part of the scope of this study.

Samenvatting

Met steeds grotere hoeveelheden hernieuwbare, fluctuerende energie, die verwacht worden tegen 2040 en 2050, is congestie van het elektriciteitsnet een lastige uitdaging voor de netbeheerders in Nederland, zowel op transmissie- als distributieniveau. Huidige mechanismen om congestie van het net te verminderen, zoals lange termijn netverzwaring, kunnen zeer kostbaar en/of onhaalbaar zijn, onder andere vanwege beschikbaarheid van land, gespecialiseerde arbeid of schaarste aan grondstoffen. Bilaterale overeenkomsten om onbalans in productie en verbruik van energie te herstellen, kunnen ook duur zijn en leiden tot situaties die meerdere partijen binnen de waardeketen beïnvloedt. De beperkingen in de beschikbaarheid van energie als gevolg van huidige en toekomstige netcongestie zijn relevant voor de businesscase van nieuwe assets die energie verbruiken, zoals elektrolyzers.

Deze studie analyseert het effect op de businesscase van een elektrolyser met contractgebaseerde strategieën op het niveau van de distributienetbeheerder (DSO). Dit is van toepassing wanneer meerdere energie assets voor elektriciteitsopwekking (zonne-energie) en -verbruik (elektrolyser) binnen dezelfde eigenaar worden gecombineerd. De gekozen casus is geïnspireerd op de H2 Hollandia-pilot in Drenthe, met 115 MW aan zonne-energie en een elektrolyser van 5 MW. Gebaseerd op het ATR85-voorstel voor transmissierechten wordt hier een vergelijkbare reeks tarieven vastgesteld: 15% van het vermogen kan op geselecteerde tijdslots worden beperkt, waar een verlaging van het nettatarief tegen overstaat (niet-vaste tarieven). Er wordt onderzocht of dit een positief effect kan hebben op de businesscase van de elektrolyser, waarbij de Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCoH) als maatstaf wordt gebruikt. Daarnaast zijn deelcasussen onderzocht die het verbruik en de opwekking beperken, is er een verkenning uitgevoerd naar verschillende relatieve groottes van de elektrolyser en naar de beschikbaarheid van het net voor een vast zonnepark en vast/niet-vast nettatarieven. Deze casussen zijn getest op twee inkoopstrategieën van groene stroom: alleen kopen bij een willekeurige bron als deze volledig groen is (met de netprijs als proxy om dit te bepalen tegen flexibele prijzen op basis van het marktstarief) of met een speciaal windpark met een vaste Power Purchase Agreement (PPA)-prijs. De expliciete impact op het distributienet in een gebied en bij een bepaald onderstation is in deze studie niet gemodelleerd en alleen kwalitatieve inzichten in dit aspect kunnen worden overwogen.

De resultaten van het onderzoek geven aan dat; als er aan de infrastructuur en andere voorwaarden (bijv. off-taker-overeenkomsten) wordt voldaan, dan kunnen nettatarieven een van de relevante prikkels zijn om waterstofproductie in specifieke gebieden te plaatsen. Het beste resultaat werd behaald met de flexibele prijsstrategie, waarbij een reductie van ongeveer 0,3 EUR/kg werd bereikt in de LCoH, bij gebruik van een variabel nettatarief in vergelijking met een vast tarief. In dit geval werd het nettatarief verlaagd van ongeveer 150 EUR/MWh naar ongeveer 70 EUR/MWh, in ruil voor minder dan 1% reductie van de benuttingsfactor van de elektrolyser vanwege de beperkingen in het verbruik.

Dit positieve effect werd echter niet altijd waargenomen. Voor de vaste PPA-strategie bleef de LCoH ongeveer constant voor vaste en variabele tarieven. Dit komt doordat de reductie van het tarief en de benuttingsfactor van de elektrolyser vergelijkbare positieve effecten, door lagere OPEX, en negatieve effecten, minder waterstofproductie, had. Er werd een bescheiden afname in de maandelijkse LCoH-profielvariabiliteit bereikt, wat resulteert in een stabielere algehele LCoH gedurende het jaar.

Het introduceren van een tweede verlagende component van het nettatarief, door het verbruikstarief verder te verlagen maar ook de opwekking te beperken (geschikt voor assets met zowel opwekking als verbruik), resulteerde niet in een positieve impact op de LCoH vergeleken met de andere flexibele tarieven voor de geteste omstandigheden.

In een onderzoek naar de optimalisatie van de grootte van de elektrolyzer capaciteit en het netaansluitings-/PPA-gebruik voor een vast zonnepark, bevorderden flexibele nettatarieven doorgaans oplossingen met meer gebruik van het net. In het geval van een vast PPA-prijstellingsschema werd een regio met grotere elektrolyzer capaciteiten (in de orde van 20 MW, vergeleken met de oorspronkelijke 5 MW) gezien als de meest kosteneffectieve oplossingen met betrekking tot de LCoH.

Dit werk benadrukt dat variabele tarieven een kans kunnen bieden om de plaatsing van elektrolyzers in bepaalde gebieden te stimuleren en/of om de businesscase van een systeem dat bestaat uit hernieuwbare energie en een elektrolyzer te verbeteren. Echter, de specifieke implementatie kan aanzienlijke aanpassingen aan elke asset/waardeketen vereisen. De bereidheid van de afnemer voor flexibele levering van waterstof, de inkoopovereenkomst strategieën en ook andere elementen die buiten het bereik van deze studie vallen, zoals energieopslagoplossingen, zijn elementen die de impact van deze tarieven grotendeels kunnen beïnvloeden. Bovendien omvatte deze studie alleen beperkingen op willekeurige tijdstippen binnen specifieke maanden en uren. In bepaalde onderstations kunnen patronen aanwezig zijn die verdere voordelen kunnen bieden, door de flexibiliteit van de asset en de contractvoorwaarden van het nettatarief af te stemmen. Deze, en een meer holistische analyse op kwalitatief/kwantitatief niveau van de kosten die gepaard gaan met het verminderen van congestie buiten de asset-eigenaar, zoals op DSO- en maatschappelijk niveau, kunnen leiden tot andere positieve effecten die geen deel uitmaakten van de scope van deze studie.

Table of contents

Document summary	2
Executive summary	4
Samenvatting.....	6
Nomenclature.....	9
1. Introduction.....	10
Research questions:	11
2. Methodology	11
2.1 Case study selection	11
2.2 Dynamic simulations and optimization of multi-energy assets: PyDOLPHYN.....	12
2.3 Techno-economic data, boundary conditions and assumptions.	13
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	14
Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCoH).	14
Monthly LCoH.....	14
2.4 Power purchase agreements (PPAs) and strategies.....	15
2.5 Grid tariffs.....	16
Non-firm tariffs for <i>consumption</i>	17
Non-firm tariffs for multi-energy assets containing consumption and generation	18
Hourly grid tariff approximation components	18
3. Results	19
3.1 Effect of adding a grid connection with a conventional grid tariff in the electrolyzer business case	19
3.2 Non-firm grid tariffs costs and effect in electrolyzer	20
3.2.1 Variable purchasing price	20
3.2.2 Fixed PPA price	22
3.2.3 Analysis of the results for variable and fixed purchasing prices	24
3.3 Non-firm grid tariffs <i>restricting generation</i>	25
3.4 Sizing optimization and its influence in the electrolyzer business case.....	27
4. Conclusions and recommendations for future work	29
4.1 Conclusions.....	29
4.2 Recommendations for future work and limitations.....	30
References.....	32

Nomenclature

Acronym	Meaning
ATR	Alternatieve transportrechten (Alternative Transport Rights)
CAPEX	Capital Expenses
DSO	Distribution System Operator
GDS	Closed Distribution System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCoH/LCOH	Levelized Cost of Hydrogen
NPV	Net Present Value
OPEX	Operational Expenses
TSO	Transmission System Operator

1. Introduction

As The Netherlands keeps building renewable energy sources, such as offshore/onshore wind and solar, its requirements for transporting this energy along and beyond the country are increasing. With 50 GW of offshore wind planned for 2040 and 70 GW for 2050, the transmission and distribution grids will face increasingly difficult challenges. In addition, onshore wind and solar and their expansion can create highly fluctuating profiles of supply/demand in certain areas/substations, resulting in grid congestion. Congestion is a challenging issue to solve. Depending on the specific region and substation, it can be related to the supply side and/or on the demand side, and range from some a few consecutive hours to days. Moreover, its predictability is also partly subjected to uncertainty in meteorological predictions and on the operation structure of the different asset owners.

The electrification of different large-scale, energy-intensive, process in industry poses difficult requirements for local and regional power grids. In addition, the concentration of onshore power generation, such as solar parks, creates highly fluctuating profiles. In the energy landscape from now up to 2050, multi-energy assets, composed of both power generation and consumption, such as a combination of solar power and an electrolyzer, are also to be expected. These assets could have a net positive or negative effect to local congestion, depending on how they are operated and how they synergize with the rest of producers and consumers at their specific substation.

Grid congestion can have a significant impact, both monetarily and socially. There is no one-size-fits-all solution for it. The first one is reinforcing the grid, by providing large investments in new infrastructure. However, this can become very expensive. From the Distribution System Operators (DSOs) perspective, an 8 BEUR total expenditure per year is planned from 2025 onwards [1]. This cost is allocated for cables, district substations, system batteries and pipes to enable a sustainable energy system. These costs end up resulting in an increase of the energy bill for the consumers, which is expected to grow up to 70% for 2030.

Part of these costs are due to the grid reinforcement needed, and a reduction of them could be achieved if alternative solutions existed where only part of these reinforcements were necessary. Monetary cost is only one of the aspects, as while this can help on a long-term basis, it can take several years to be fulfilled. Moreover, shortages of raw materials of technical workers, and the different procedures to be taken, can result in unexpected delays.

There are other mechanisms that are already in place in order to relieve grid congestion. Redispatch can be performed. In The Netherlands, there are two market-based ways of doing so. The first one is RESIN, the Reserve for Other Purposes (Reservevermogen Overige Doeleinden, ROD). In this case, TenneT is the single buyer. Market participants with 60 MW of connection are required to submit bids to the system. This system is optional for parties with more than 1 MW and less than 60 MW. There is a bid system for re-dispatching and balancing. If re-dispatching is accepted, balancing is withdrawn. Redispatch is “pay-as-bid”. GOPACS is an alliance between DSOs (Stedin, Liander, Enexis and Westland Infra), TenneT and the intraday trading platform ETPA. Using this platform, intraday bids for redispatching can be submitted. Buy and sell orders that are not matched can go to GOPACS. At the moment of the publication of this study, its influence in local grid congestion is limited, with less than 100 redispatching orders in 2024. In addition, an asset owner can also be called individually to perform redispatching. This is a labour-intensive, usually manual process, also associated with compensation mechanisms that can become very costly for the DSOs.

From the perspective of contract-based mechanisms, Capacity limitation contracts (CBC, capaciteitsbeperkingscontract) can also be set. These contracts can limit the use of the connection and

the transport capacity for a certain period. In exchange, a financial compensation can be set. In 2024, a draft decision for the Alternatieve transportrechten (ATR) was set by the Autoriteit Consument & Markt (ACM), on the proposal of Netbeheer Nederland for two new alternative transmission rights. The time-bound transport right allows the connected party to transport for 85% of the hours (ATR85) on an annual basis on TenneT's high-voltage grid. On the other hand, the time-block-related transmission right enables the party to use the transmission system within certain time blocks.

Following the spirit of this ATR85 rule, it is aimed to be explored in this study *if flexible contracts at the DSO levels could also benefit grid congestion, focusing in the business case of an electrolyzer in a standalone area that could be connected to the grid.* This could encourage to bring an asset that consumes power in a flexible way, such as an electrolyzer, in areas with existing grid congestion. It could also affect its operation to be more beneficial to the grid, so part of the grid reinforcements may be avoided.

Research questions:

1. *What is the effect (technical and economical, such as load factor and levelized costs of hydrogen) of adding a grid connection for an electrolyzer present in a standalone area?*
2. *How do flexible DSO tariffs affect the business case of the electrolyzer compared to conventional tariffs?*
3. *How do these tariffs affect the business case for different power purchase agreements types?*
4. *What additional incentives can be provided for multi-energy assets (power generation and consumptions) via tariff schemes to further improve grid congestion?*
5. *How do these tariffs influence the optimum electrolyzer size for a given renewable power size? Do they affect the size of other agreements, such as green power consumed from the grid or a Power Purchase Agreement?*

To answer these questions, a two-step approach has been taken:

- Firstly, consultations were made with relevant stakeholders, in order to choose a suitable case study and gather input data, used for the techno-economic figures and the boundary conditions of the case.
- Afterwards, the system was modelled using dynamic simulations for the system on an hourly basis. The techno-economical KPIs and the energy flows were calculated for a variety of subcases, including different grid tariff schemes, power purchase strategies and electrolyzer sizes.

2. Methodology

2.1 Case study selection

The case study was selected from the list of the standalone hydrogen areas explored in D2a.1 of this HyDelta 3.0 work package. The suitability to choose a particular case study was done using the following criteria:

- Dedicated combination of renewable energy and hydrogen production planned.
- Possibilities for multiple potential grid tariff schemes (e.g., cable pooling).
- Potential flexibility at both the producer and the off-taker.
- Possibilities to expand the system in the future, such as increasing the size of the electrolyzer.

- Value chain complexity: a very complex value chain would shift the focus of the study to modelling the chain itself, not leaving enough room to analyse the impact of several tariff schemes or size combinations.
- Availability of data and boundary conditions.

Figure 2.1: Case study location (left, graph from [2]) and schematic of energy flows (right).

The case study chosen is inspired by H2 Hollandia, located in Nieuw-Buinen, Drenthe. It is connected to the closed distribution system (GDS) of Avebe. The electrolyzer is “behind the solar farm”, with no grid connection. A schematic overview of the case can be seen in Figure 2.1. The solar farm is significantly oversized with respect to the electrolyzer. There are several reasons for this choice, including technology availability, cost and energy flows analysis. A detailed overview of this case study can be found in D2a.1 of this work [2]. While the electrolyzer is not connected directly to the electricity grid, the possibility exists to do this in the future.

It should be noted that this case study is taken as an *inspiration* for the calculations performed. A system with similar, simplified energy flows to this case study has been modelled, with internal considerations for techno-economic and performance figures. The results shown do not necessarily represent the reality of operating the H2 Hollandia system, due to the lack of proprietary data and a feedback loop with the asset owner. This includes cost figures, performance figures of the components, but also boundary conditions such as energy prices and hourly grid congestion figures at the specific substation. This work aims to represent an overview of the impact of grid tariffs in a system *with similar sizes and connections* as H2 Hollandia for *generic, prescribed* flexibility preconditions.

2.2 Dynamic simulations and optimization of multi-energy assets: PyDOLPHYN

PyDOLPHYN is a TNO-developed modelling framework for dynamic simulations and optimization of multi-energy assets [3-5]. It allows to find a cost-effective optimal result, that may have been impossible to find when running static simulations on value chains or focusing only on the dynamics of an individual asset component. PyDOLPHYN combines component-level physics and techno-economics, and it can be used in system integration, asset design and operation studies. The framework is based on connections of physical blocks, each of them representing one component

(e.g., electrolyzer, battery, storage, water desalination). With PyDOLPHYN, optimal asset sizing and operation can be computed, adhering to physical bottlenecks, such as transient effects and dynamic efficiency levels. It can use dynamic pricing for the different energy vectors (e.g., electricity, hydrogen) and complex constraints. With this, control strategies can be defined for both short and long-term predictions (e.g., pre-emptively store hydrogen to sell it at the highest value for the market/off-taker), and to the fidelity of techno-economic KPIs can be improved.

In this project, PyDOLPHYN was used to calculate the energy flows and the interactions between the different components. It can provide complementary insights to a qualitative analysis and static simulations (with fixed efficiency, simple constraints, etc.), regarding the volatility of the different energy sources and a more realistic quantification of the KPIs. As an example, Figure 2.2 shows the comparison between a static and a dynamic analysis where a hydrogen storage volume is aimed to be optimized: these static calculations do not consider the dynamics along the year, and can lead to either too small (infeasible design, failing to provide security of supply, as in the graph) or too large (very expensive) sizes. In the future energy landscape, where these dynamics are expected to play a prominent role, it is important to integrate them from early stages.

Figure 2.2: Example of an optimized hydrogen storage volume using PyDOLPHYN.

2.3 Techno-economic data, boundary conditions and assumptions.

The data used to simulate the system is a combination of internal TNO simulations and other projections for 2030.

The costs for the different components are based on internal assumptions, partially based on reports based on current costs on electrolysis-based systems ([6], [7]).

Table 1: Assumptions taken for the different components of the system.

Component	Value
Electrolyzer CAPEX [EUR/W]	3.0
Electrolyzer OPEX [% of CAPEX/y]	4.03
Lifetime [y]	25
Discount rate	8%
Electrolyzer technology	PEM
Electrolyzer minimum load	20%
Electrolyzer nominal specific energy consumed [kWh/kg H ₂]	50.5

For the power input (solar as part of the system and wind via a PPA out of the system) and the market data, the meteorological year 2009 was used as a reference. The results obtained using 1-hour simulations for the whole year are then extrapolated using the discount rate to the lifetime of the asset.

The solar profile was obtained with the default settings of PVGIS 5.3 in the vicinity of the H2 Hollandia location (PVGIS-SARAH3 database [8], [9], [10]). The wind profile was obtained from the TNO CFD tool FarmFlow [11], with a DOWA profile in the Dutch North Sea.

Market prices were obtained from the EYE tool from TNO, using as a reference capacities of different energy assets aligned with a 2030 approximation of the Global Ambition scenario of the Ten Year Network Development Plan [12]. This scenario focus on a global economy with low-carbon and renewable energy supply options on a centralized level.

The capacities from this scenario for supply and demand are used to simulate a power market in 2030, providing as an output hourly prices for power. These prices are used in the PyDOLPHYN framework to determine expenses if power from the grid is purchased.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Within this document, a series of KPIs will be shown.

Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCoH).

To obtain the LCoH, the net present value (NPV) of the sum of costs over the lifetime of the asset is divided by the net present value of the hydrogen produced, as

$$LCoH = \frac{NPV_{costs}}{NPV_{H_2}}$$

where the first term takes into account the CAPEX and OPEX of the electrolyzer, the solar power used for it from the 115 MW park (assumed to be purchased at market rate), any other power purchased from the grid (at market rate or with a fixed PPA price) and the grid tariffs.

Monthly LCoH

An assumption of this study is that the purchase price of the hydrogen production by the off-taker follows a variable monthly price. Without knowledge of how this is done in practice in the commercial agreement between H2 Hollandia and the off-taker, it is assumed that the monthly prices take into account monthly grid tariff and power purchase price variations, with the rest of the components spread uniformly over the lifetime of the asset. Due to the fact that the simulation only includes one year, to give an accurate representation of the absolute number of these monthly costs, some scaling needs to be performed. This is done by

$$LCoH_{monthly} = LCoH_{monthly_{original}} \cdot \frac{LCoH_{total}}{\overline{LCoH_{monthly}}}$$

Where $\overline{LCoH_{monthly}}$ represents the mean value of the monthly original LCoH values calculated.

2.4 Power purchase agreements (PPAs) and strategies

If not enough solar power is available to fulfil the minimum load of the electrolyzer, it is assumed that it is possible to purchase power from the grid, with a certain agreement/pricing. In this study, two types of purchase strategies have been tested, both using different sources of green power.

The first one is a fixed-price PPA, reserving capacity from a particular wind farm of a certain capacity, up to the maximum capacity of the electrolyzer. It includes two components: a base price and a capacity-based price. The reasoning is that it may be commercially beneficial to reserve power from a wind farm *larger* than the electrolyzer. As an example, the first 5 MW produced of a 100 MW wind farm could be reserved, increasing the load factor of the electrolyzer over purchasing 5 MW from a 5 MW wind farm. However, as the first MW of the load curve are the more expensive ones in PPAs, this comes with a penalty in price. This is represented in the formula

$$PPA_{fixedprice} = PPA_{base} \cdot [1 + \alpha_{overcapacitywind} \cdot \max\left(0.0, \frac{wind_{capacity}}{electrolyzer_{capacity}} - 1\right)],$$

Where PPA_{base} was set to 60 EUR/MWh, and $\alpha_{overcapacitywind}$ was set to 0.25.

The second type of purchase strategy uses as a basis the EU Delegated Acts on Renewable Hydrogen [14]. In this strategy, it is assumed that the grid is composed of green energy if the grid price is below a certain threshold, set to 0.36 times the price of tonne of CO₂, or 32.4 EUR/MWh for the 2030 simulation. In this strategy, there is no fixed source of green power, and it is assumed that it is possible to buy up to the nominal capacity of the electrolyzer if this threshold condition is satisfied.

Figure 2.3: Market prices simulated for 2030, clipped to 0-100 EUR/MWh for visualization purposes. The mean value of this simulation is around 64 EUR/MWh. Note that due to the nature of the operational strategies, only prices below 32.4 EUR/MWh are used to purchase electricity.

2.5 Grid tariffs

Figure 2.4: Example of a breakdown of grid tariffs, used as a reference in this study. The values of these tariffs may differ depending on the DSO and the year considered, and should be seen as qualitative.

An overview of the components of the grid tariffs considered in this study is shown in Figure 2.4. In this case, the one-time and periodic costs are not considered (one-time due to being equal for all strategies, and periodic connection fee largely eliminated by cable pooling). The analysis focuses on the contributions of the contracted power and the maximum peak power. The reference values used in the conventional grid tariff analysis are 2 EUR/kW/month for the contracted power and 3 EUR/kW/month for the maximum peak power. These values should be seen as *qualitative*, as the exact number depend on factors such as the exact number considered, specific conditions, the DSO, and the year taken as a reference in the simulation. As seen in the figure, some of the other tariff components have not been included in the analysis. Those components are fixed for a given connection, regardless of its utilization, and would only scale the absolute values of the results.

In addition to quantifying these grid tariffs, two proposals of flexible tariffs have been defined in the simulations, inspired by the *alternatieve transportrechten (ATR85)* proposal [15].

Non-firm tariffs for *consumption*

Figure 2.5: Non-firm grid tariff plans per hour, original taken as inspiration (top, modification of a reconstructed graph from [15]) and simplification applied in this study (bottom).

In these schemes, there are two differences with respect to the conventional tariffs:

- The operator can restrict the usage of the grid for up to 15% of the time annually. The regions where this is expected can be seen in Figure 2.5, in red. The restrictions can happen during 16 hours a day (8:00-00:00) for 6 months in the year (January-March and October-December).
- As a counterpart, if power is consumed outside of the red areas, there is a reduction of the *monthly peak* component, kW_{max} . This reduction is the multiplying factor seen in the figure (0.7) if no power is consumed in the red area during that month. If power is consumed in the red area, a linear weighted average of the reduction factor depending on the usage on each of the two regions is applied.

In addition, two sub-schemes have been proposed for the contracted power ($kW_{contract}$) component:

- Non-firm grid 1: a tariff reduction is given based on the average monthly consumption, instead of a fixed contracted power.
- Non-firm grid 2: no fixed tariff for contracted power. This can be seen as the upper limit of the benefits that can be achieved via modifying this component in terms of tariff reductions.

In the simulations, a pseudo-random number generator was used to sample 15% of time steps where this restriction can occur. To provide a fair comparison, the seed for the sampling was fixed, such as all simulations are restricted in the same time steps.

Non-firm tariffs for multi-energy assets containing consumption and generation

At the moment, there are no grid tariffs associated for delivering solar power to the grid. However, congestion can happen both on the supply and the demand side, depending on the particular substation. For parties that own assets connected to the same substation that generate and consume power, an additional mechanism may be able to be used from a grid tariff perspective to *also restrict power deployment to the grid*. This additional tariff reduction may be able to encourage the asset owner to accept flexible curtailment of power, on top of any other agreement already present with the DSO.

Figure 2.6: Grid tariff reduction for non-firm tariffs restricting consumption and generation.

The tariff reduction explored follows a similar philosophy as in the previous section. Figure 2.6 shows the reduction in the peak power component analyzed in this case. This symmetric restriction has some limitations that limit how representative they are of an actual situation: depending on the specific substation, it may be supply or demand-restricted for a larger part of the time; these two restrictions do not occur in the same moments in time in reality; and there are no patterns present, such as characteristic time scales for length of the restricted periods. Nevertheless, it serves as a first step for this comparison, which can be further refined in further work in collaboration with a DSO.

Hourly grid tariff approximation components

In the comparison of the firm and non-firm tariffs, approximations have been made to the monthly profiles in order to obtain hourly profiles. The following approximations apply:

- Only the maximum peak power component has been modified hourly.
- This component is modified using the scaling map for the grid tariff reductions (Figure 2.5).
- Hourly grid tariffs are shown in EUR/MWh, corresponding to the consumption at that particular hour. Due to this, the hourly grid tariffs are only shown for moments when grid power is consumed, and are scaled depending on how many hours the grid was used during the month.

3. Results

3.1 Effect of adding a grid connection with a conventional grid tariff in the electrolyzer business case

Figure 3.1: LCOH contributions of each of the cost components for each of the grid connection strategies and conventional grid tariffs.

The effect of adding a grid connection to the business case of the electrolyzer is very dependent on the type of strategy used to purchase power from the grid. As seen in Figure 3.1, the strategy with a variable purchasing price achieves a very similar total LCOH compared to the reference case with no grid connection. This is due to the fact that a limited amount of power is purchased. This limited power is due to the price curve used: there are not many instances during the year below the green power threshold *and* not enough solar power. If using a different price curve for different conditions, such as a 2040 projections (with more wind power available than the 2030 scenario), more instances where green power can be purchased are to be expected. The power bought in this case is relatively inexpensive, due to the threshold set, but this increase in load factor is offset with the cost of the grid tariff. Conversely, adding a fixed PPA with a dedicated wind farm of 5 MW capacity significantly decreases the LCoH and the relative contribution of the grid tariff to it. These results highlight that the benefits of other grid tariffs from the perspective of the business case of the electrolyzer could range from very limited to significant, depending on the purchasing strategy.

The monthly profiles of the LCoH can be observed in Figure 3.2. Both no grid and variable purchasing price strategies follow a similar trend: an increasing availability of solar power correlates with a decrease in the LCoH (around March-September). The fixed PPA strategy shows that the wind power availability has a larger influence in this case. In all cases, the higher peaks in LCoH also correlate with months with no/limited power purchased, and a significantly lower LCoH is achieved overall.

Figure 3.2: Monthly profiles of LCOH for each of the strategies with no grid/firm grid tariffs.

3.2 Non-firm grid tariffs costs and effect in electrolyzer

3.2.1 Variable purchasing price

Figure 3.3 shows the energy flows towards the electrolyzer. In this case, there is a small percentage of energy bought from the grid, as seen in the previous section.

Figure 3.3: Energy sent to the electrolyzer for different grid tariff schemes (variable purchasing price strategy).

Figure 3.4 compares the different grid tariff schemes. The electrolyzer utilization factor slightly increases when using the grid, as previously discussed. Looking at the right graph, it seems that a large reduction in the grid tariff cost in EUR/MWh can be achieved by switching to flexible schemes. The reduction in the load factor of the electrolyzer is negligible, while the grid tariff component reduces to almost half of the original amount. Both non-firm tariffs, 1 (mean power over the month used for the calculation of the kW_contract component) and 2 (no kW_contract component), perform similarly. This very small difference between non-firm 1 and 2 is related to the calculation method utilized. The small amount of purchased power makes the kW contract component less important in relative terms to the kW max component.

Figure 3.4: Electrolyzer utilization factor (left) and grid tariff component (right) for different grid tariff schemes (variable purchasing price strategy).

The reduction in the grid tariffs is positively reflected in the LCOH, as observed in Figure 3.5. **While the firm tariff has a similar LCOH than having no grid at all, both flexible schemes provide a clear improvement, in the order of 0.3 EUR/kg.**

Figure 3.5: LCOH contributions of each of the cost components for each of the grid tariff schemes (variable purchasing price strategy).

Figure 3.6 shows the hourly approximations of the grid tariffs for the three different schemes. Due to the relatively small amount of power purchased, these approximations do not provide very distinct trends.

Figure 3.6: Hourly grid tariff approximations for the three different tariff schemes (fixed PPA strategy). Note: the lines connect consecutive hours when the grid is used, and hours with no grid consumption are not shown.

Looking in more detail at the hourly profiles for selected months (Figure 3.7), provides additional insight over the continuity of these profiles. Only in very specific occasions there are more than 5 consecutive hours with power purchased, when the grid tariff changes from the full to the discounted rate or vice versa.

Figure 3.7: Detailed overview of the hourly grid tariff approximations for four different months for firm and non-firm tariff schemes (variable purchasing price strategy). Note: the lines connect consecutive hours when the grid is used, and hours with no grid consumption are not shown

3.2.2 Fixed PPA price

For a fixed PPA price, Figure 3.8 shows the energy sent to the electrolyzer for the three cases. The results are very different than in the previous case. It can be observed how 43% (firm grid) and 40% (non-firm grid) of the energy is bought from the PPA with the wind farm. This difference between firm and non-firm tariffs is due to the 15% of the time that power cannot be purchased in the non-firm tariff schemes.

Figure 3.8: Energy sent to the electrolyzer for different grid tariff schemes (fixed PPA strategy).

This results in an increase of the utilization factor, as seen in Figure 3.9. Conversely to the previous case, there is a 6% difference in the utilization factor for firm and non-firm tariffs. As the grid is used for a significantly higher amount of time compared to a variable purchase agreement, this difference between both tariffs is also amplified. The reduction of the load factor correlates quite well to the amount of time that this flexibility is imposed: there is a 16.9% in reduction in power purchased from the grid due to the 15% of the time that the flexibility condition is imposed.

Figure 3.9: Electrolyzer utilization factor (left) and grid tariff component (right) for different grid tariff schemes (fixed PPA strategy).

The grid tariff contribution in EUR/MWh can be significantly reduced by using the non-firm schemes, as seen in the right part of Figure 3.9. It should be noted that these tariffs (for fixed PPA-based strategies) are around 5-7 times lower than in the variable purchasing price case. Hence, while this reduction can still provide a benefit, it does not have the same impact. This is highlighted in Figure 3.10: the lowest LCoH are achieved with both firm tariffs and the non-firm tariff 2 (*no kW_contract*). For the non-firm grid tariff 1, the reduction in grid tariff cannot offset the decrease in the utilization factor of the electrolyzer, and with it, the potential revenue that can be achieved. All of the grid tariffs, regardless of their flexibility, achieve a reduction in the LCoH compared to not using grid power.

Figure 3.10: LCOH contributions of each of the cost components for each of the grid tariff schemes (fixed PPA strategy).

Hourly approximations for the different tariffs are shown in Figure 3.11. The non-firm tariffs provide less variability in the monthly profiles. In this case, the peak power consumption is the most contributing factor with the non-firm schemes.

Figure 3.11: Hourly grid tariff approximations for the three different tariff schemes (fixed PPA strategy). Note: the lines connect consecutive hours when the grid is used, and hours with no grid consumption are not shown.

When looking at the profiles for different months with significant variability (January, March, October and December), Figure 3.12 shows the typical behaviour of an asset connected to an oversized solar park. The main dynamics have daily profiles. These are associated with the reductions in the peak power tariff component at certain times. As the figure shows the grid tariffs in EUR/MWh, the fluctuations of the wind profile are not appreciated. In this case, the hourly variations account for around 5 EUR/MWh in the month where grid tariff reductions apply in different hours.

Figure 3.12: Detailed overview of the hourly grid tariff approximations for four different months for firm and non-firm tariff schemes (fixed PPA prices). Note: the lines connect consecutive hours when the grid is used, and hours with no grid consumption are not shown.

3.2.3 Analysis of the results for variable and fixed purchasing prices

As seen in the previous sections, there is a clear difference in the effect of the non-firm grid tariffs on the business case of the electrolyzer depending on the purchasing strategy used. For a variable purchasing price with the threshold set for green energy, both flexible tariff schemes can provide a significant reduction in the LCoH compared to firm tariffs (around 0.3 EUR/kg). Conversely, the positive effect is less clear for a fixed PPA price: the reductions in the LCoH are negligible, and the best result could be achieved with either firm or non-firm schemes slightly changing one of the input parameters, such as the scaling factor in the non-firm agreements.

There are limitations for this reasoning. Firstly, only LCoH has been explored as a metric. This ignores the potential revenues that can be achieved, and ignores potential non-linearities that exist in the agreement between the hydrogen producer and the off-taker. If, similarly to energy purchased in other markets, providing a base load of hydrogen supply holds a higher monetary value than the

peak load fluctuations, then this reduction in the utilization factor may have a more limited effect in the LCoH, increasing the relative positive effect of the tariff reduction for a non-firm scheme.

Even with the limitations of this study, a mild positive effect in the monthly fluctuations of the LCoH for the fixed PPA case (Figure 3.13). The non-firm schemes are slightly more stable throughout the year, as the contributions of the reduced tariff and the availability of the green power cancel each other out up to a certain extent. This effect could be potentially amplified in the revenues if variable hydrogen prices, correlated to other commodities, were also considered.

Figure 3.13: LCoH monthly profiles for different tariff schemes (fixed PPA price).

These results highlight that the non-firm tariffs potentially provide benefits for both the DSO and the electrolyzer business case. However, it is not evident in all cases. A bilateral communication between DSO and the hydrogen producer, with knowledge of the purchasing strategy and other limitations on the system (such as seasonal effects in the substation), could provide fit-for-purpose tariffs that tailor better to the particular situation.

The type of contract with the off-taker is another element that is out of scope in the current study, and that could also provide enhanced benefits, if it is aligned with the grid tariff scheme (e.g., accept a higher supply when the grid tariffs are lower). The trade-offs for the off-taker in this situation are also out of the scope of the study. Moreover, societal costs/benefits are out of scope as well. Without including these elements, it is difficult to provide a quantitative assessment of the benefits for the value chain, even if qualitative there is a positive potential.

3.3 Non-firm grid tariffs restricting generation

In this section, a contract scheme suitable for a multi-energy asset owner (power consumption and generation) is tested, limiting *both* symmetrically. This comes associated with a further reduction in the tariffs *for consumption*. This restriction is applied *up to the capacity of the electrolyzer*. In this case, 5 MW of the solar power can be curtailed.

Figure 3.14: Solar power: original, curtailable due to non-firm scheme and curtailed (left), and percentage of solar power curtailed up to the electrolyzer capacity (right).

An overview of the curtailment on the generation side can be observed in Figure 3.14. The seasonal profile is observed, which is slightly beneficial from the solar power perspective. The power curtailed results in a loss of the utilization factor of the *first 5 MW of solar power* of 12% (not of the whole solar farm, as only 5 MW out of the total capacity of 115 MW is curtailed), in the 15% of the time that the restriction can apply. This effect is exacerbated if the ratio between both is smaller: 8.2% for a 20 MW electrolyzer, and reaching a minimum of around 2.2%. At very high ratios between solar and electrolyzer capacity, there is a slight increase. This is due to the fact that there are more instances where there is not enough solar power to satisfy the minimum load of the electrolyzer and it is aimed to be sent to the grid instead compared to the cases with a ratio around 0.6, where the majority of the power in these instances is used to power the electrolyzer.

This highlights that, **for certain ratios between solar and electrolyzer capacities, grid tariff schemes that benefit from the seasonality effects between solar generation and substation congestion could potentially provide beneficial effects:** small decreases in the utilization factor of the solar power with a significant decrease in congestion in the selected time slots.

Figure 3.15: Comparison between the cost savings of the grid tariffs with/without restricting generation for variable (left) and fixed (right) power purchase price.

When applying these schemes (non-firm generation 1 and 2) for a 5 MW electrolyzer, Figure 3.15 shows that both purchasing strategies (variable and fixed prices) perform worse in the cost savings compared to the previous non-firm tariffs tested before (non-firm 1 and 2). This incentive is *not*

enough to provide additional cost savings compared to the non-firm schemes described before. This is due to the fact that the loss of the power revenue (*assuming that this power could be sold to the market*) is too large to overcome the savings in the grid tariff. Nevertheless, the cost balance compared to the *firm* scheme can still be positive for the variable purchasing price strategy.

For a different set of assumptions, this result may vary. For example, if in some instances the asset owner were to need to curtail anyways due to congestion at the substation, the revenue stream shown in the figures above would be significantly smaller, and the balance compared to the other non-firm tariffs may become positive.

3.4 Sizing optimization and its influence in the electrolyzer business case

This last section of results corresponds to a sizing optimization on the electrolyzer capacity and its corresponding grid utilization. The objective function is the minimization of the LCoH. A limitation of this optimization is that, while the LCoH of the generation-restricted cases may be a bit lower, they do not consider the loss of revenue due to the solar power curtailed. Hence, this should be seen as a qualitative, exploratory analysis of the *upper ceiling* of the benefits that could be achieved with such a scheme.

Figure 3.16: Optimum electrolyzer capacity for different grid tariff schemes (variable purchasing price strategy).

Figure 3.16 shows the first case, for variable purchasing prices. In this case, switching to flexible tariffs results in reductions in the absolute LCoH for a fixed configuration. However, the optimum electrolyzer size is found in all cases for 5 MW (reference case). A difference, as seen before, is that the firm contract promotes *no grid connection at all* as the optimum, while the optimum for the non-firm schemes is found with a grid connection equal to the size of the electrolyzer. In this figure, a triangle is set covering half of the parameter space. This region is non-physical, as in this purchasing strategy, the grid capacity can only be as large as the electrolyzer capacity.

Figure 3.17: Optimum electrolyzer capacity for different grid tariff schemes (fixed purchasing price strategy). The pink diamonds represent the optimum solution found.

The optimum results are significantly different for the fixed PPA price, as observed in Figure 3.17. The optimum region for the firm contract is in the vicinity of the reference case. Switching to non-firm contracts shifts the optimum to larger electrolyzer sizes, of around 12-14 MW, with wind farm capacities of around the same size of the electrolyzer.

4. Conclusions and recommendations for future work

4.1 Conclusions

In this work, different grid tariff schemes with realistic hydrogen production profiles and market price estimations have been implemented, looking at the added value of non-firm contracts. Hourly profiles were used, using a variable efficiency curve with a physical model for the electrolyzer and power/market curves. A comparison between non-grid-connected, firm and two types of flexible tariff schemes has been studied: limiting only consumption and limiting consumption + generation, with two types of agreements for power purchase (market rate and fixed PPA price). The main conclusions that can be drawn are:

- Using non-firm grid tariffs can provide a significant reduction in their cost per unit of grid power purchased (in EUR/MWh), while still having a close utilization factor in the electrolyzer to the firm tariff cases. Reductions of 40-50% in grid tariff costs were obtained, while only limiting the utilization factor of the electrolyzer by less than 1% (flexible pricing) and 5% (fixed pricing) compared to firm tariffs.
- The impact of the non-firm tariffs in the business case of the electrolyzer based on the LCoH can vary depending on the purchasing strategy from the grid.
 - o For the tariffs limiting consumption and variable purchasing prices, having a grid-connected electrolyzer results in a similar LCoH compared to not purchasing power from the grid (0.03 EUR/kg difference). However, switching to non-firm tariffs provides a reduction of 0.3 EUR/kg compared to firm tariffs. Comparing using the mean consumption for the *kW contract* component versus eliminating it completely (non-firm 1 and 2) results in negligible differences. The reductions in the LCoH are related to a reduction in the grid tariff costs, from 148 EUR/MWh to 69-72 EUR/MWh, for less than 1% reduction of the utilization factor of the electrolyzer due to the restrictions in consumption.
 - o The positive effect of non-firm tariffs is less clear with a fixed PPA. In this case, the utilization factor is significantly larger (0.75 for firm contract, 0.69 for non-firm contracts), so while the *relative* impact in grid tariff can result in more than 40% reductions, its *absolute* impact in the business case of the electrolyzer is much lower (EUR/MWh costs of 11-21). While having a grid-connected electrolyzer was always beneficial in this strategy (around 6.6 compared to the 8.0 EUR/kg LCoH for non-grid-connected), all firm and non-firm contracts have a similar LCoH.
- Non-firm grid tariffs achieved a modest decrease in the variability of the monthly values of the LCoH. This might be relevant for an off-taker if the price agreements are updated at this rate. Other LCoH figures (weekly, seasonal) have not been explored.
- Providing a larger reduction in grid tariff in exchange for reducing consumption *and* generation did not provide a reduction in the LCoH for the case regarding 115 MW of solar power and 5 MW of an electrolyzer. While the impact in the business case was not positive with the parameters tested, it could be seen that from an energy flows perspective, there could be some potential for different schemes in this regard. When increasing the size of the electrolyzer compared to the solar park, only a very small part of the solar power would be curtailed in key moments (around 2.2% of the total curtailable power in 15% of the hours in a year), while providing significant reductions in the grid tariff component. Other types of non-firm tariff schemes for assets containing both generation and consumption in certain

substations could be beneficial (e.g., if the assets affecting the congestion have a different profile than the solar park).

- The sizing optimization analysis reflected that with the variable purchasing price strategy, adding non-firm tariffs promotes using the grid, while firm tariffs result in the lowest LCoH when no grid power is used. For the fixed PPA, a larger region of close-to-optimum electrolyzer sizes can be found, up to 12-14 MW.
- **This work suggests that, if the infrastructure and other conditions (e.g., off-taker agreements) are present, grid tariffs could be one of the relevant incentives (in combination with others) to bring hydrogen production to certain areas, as potentially larger than the 0.3 EUR/kg reductions in the LCoH could be achieved.** However, this is unlikely to be sufficient with a single tariff scheme. A customized, fit-for-purpose agreement per customer considering the amount of times for the restriction, their length, and the off-taker willingness to accept variable output, are elements that will largely influence this. This could be particularly relevant if substations in the vicinity of the original planned location have different congestion profiles that could benefit of the flexibility provided by an electrolyzer operating at variable load factors.

4.2 Recommendations for future work and limitations

This study can be seen as a first step towards understanding the impact of non-firm tariffs in a system composed of a solar park and an electrolyzer. However, due to its limited scope, there are several limitations associated with it, that could be improved and explored in future work:

- This study only focused on the direct impact of the business case of the electrolyzer. A more thorough analysis of the combined business case of the multi-energy asset (power generation and consumption) could result in different optimum configurations and impact of tariffs.
- Simplifications have been made with only two hourly regions (high and low grid tariffs). A more fine-grained mapping could provide results that are in between conventional and simplified ATR.
- Each substation has its own particular boundary conditions and length of restrictions. In this study, no characteristic time with no connection has been explored. The 15% restrictions were sampled randomly out of all time steps when congestion may be expected.
- Only ATR-based models have been explored as options. No other capacity-limiting schemes have been explored so far. In addition, 15% of the time as a restriction may be not sufficient/too large, depending on the specific substation. A sensitivity of this parameter has not been studied. In addition, the time bands where the restrictions can happen were fixed. Depending on the particular profiles of the energy generation and consumption at the substation, these bands could be increasingly complex, and need their own customized assessment.
- The effect of intermittency on other operational aspects on the electrolyzer has not been explored. Depending on the technology (alkaline, proton-exchange membrane, solid oxide) and operating procedures, the strategies tested here may not be feasible.
- No intermediate purchasing options have been explored. The variable and fixed price purchasing strategies had very different utilization factors (0.46 and 0.75, respectively, in the highest usage cases). In addition, PPA agreements of partial loads of the electrolyzer (e.g., to keep it at least at minimum load at close to all times) were not in scope.
- Hourly data for the specific grid congestion expected in the region was not gathered. This means that while the study can be seen as a generic expected result for an installation in the

Netherlands, its results cannot directly translate to the specific business case of the local project used as an inspiration (H2 Hollandia). The assumptions made compound on this uncertainty: if simulated market data for 2030 is used with a certain green energy mix, then also simulations of expected grid congestion in the area based on supply/demand/infrastructure development should be made.

- The impact from a societal perspective, as well as the DSO costs/savings has not been quantified. While there are clear qualitative benefits associated with the flexible tariffs qualitatively, it has not been quantified the monetary savings made by applying them.
- The full array of incentives to bring an electrolyzer to a congested area has not been explored: there are other market mechanisms (potentially bilateral between DSO-asset owner, or with agreements via subsidies) that are not part of the study.
- Other flexibility assets, such as adding a battery to the system, could increase the impact of these flexible tariffs. This was out of scope in the current analysis.

References

- [1] Netbeheer Nederland, “Nationale uitvoeringsagenda regionale infrastructuur,” 1 November 2023. [Online]. Available: https://www.netbeheernederland.nl/publicatie/nationale-uitvoeringsagenda-regionale-infrastructuur?_gl=1*2kmqk2*_up*MQ..*_ga*MTgyMTQxODE4MC4xNzI4OTA0NjQ3*_ga_C4KC7RL1SC*MTcyODkwNDY0Ny4xLjAuMTcyODkwNDY0Ny4wLjAuMA...
- [2] R. van Zoelen, N. Dooley and D. van Boer, “HyDelta 3.0 D2a.1 – The role of standalone hydrogen areas in decentral hydrogen,” 2024.
- [3] J. Fatou Gómez and N. González Díez, “Pydolphins: Dynamic modelling of VRE assets”, Beyond Borders: The North West European Collaboration., 2021.
- [4] V. V. Dighe, J. Fatou Gómez, S. Dussi, J. Poort and P. Shoeibi Omrani, “Digitalization of North Sea Energy Systems”, North Sea Energy, 2022.
- [5] J. Fatou Gómez, Alejandro Martín-Gil, S. Dussi, “PyDOLPHYN: Dynamic simulations and optimization of multi-energy assets”, *In review*.
- [6] L. Eblé and M. Weeda, “Evaluation of the levelised cost of hydrogen based on proposed electrolyser projects in the Netherlands,” 2024.
- [7] BloombergNEF, “Electrolyzer price survey 2024: Rising Costs, Glitchy Tech,” 2024.
- [8] M. Šúri and J. Hofierka, “A new GIS-based solar radiation model and its application to photovoltaic assessments,” 2004.
- [9] M. Šúri, T. Huld and E. Dunlop, “PV-GIS: A web based solar radiation database for the calculation of PV potential in Europe,” 2005.
- [10] European Commission, “Photovoltaic Geographical Information System,” [Online]. Available: https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/en/.
- [11] E. Bot and S. Kanev, “Farmflow: Extensively validated and dedicated model for wind farm control,” TNO, 2020.
- [12] ENTO-E and ENTSOG, “TYNDP // 2024 Draft Scenarios Report,” May 2024. [Online]. Available: https://2024.entsos-tyndp-scenarios.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/TYNDP_2024_Draft_Scenarios_Report_May_2024_240708_web.pdf. [Accessed 10 12 2024].
- [13] Netbeheer Nederland, “Het energiesysteem van de toekomst: de I13050-scenario's,” Netbeheer Nederland, 2023.
- [14] European Commission, “Questions and Answers on the EU Delegated Acts on Renewable Hydrogen,” 2023. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_23_595.

- [15] Netbeheer Nederland, “Voorstel Netbeheer Nederland tijdsafhankelijke tarieven,” 16 11 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.acm.nl/system/files/documents/voorstel-netbeheer-nederland-voor-tijdsafhankelijke-tarieven.pdf>. [Accessed 10 12 2024].